

Runcinia erythrina Jézéquel, 1964 one of the typical grassland spider species from South Africa revisited (Araneae: Thomisidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, Allen Jones² and Peter Webb³‡

¹ Project manager SANSА, dippenaaransie@gmail.com; ²SANSА Free State team member; ³ SANSА Gauteng Team member

ABSTRACT: *Runcinia erythrina* Jézéquel 1964 is a typical grassland species with a wide distribution. It is known from the Ivory Coast in the Afrotropical Region to South Africa in the south. It is presently known from eight provinces in South Africa. The female, with her characteristic decorated abdomen, is easily recognized. More information on its morphology, lifestyle, distribution, and conservation status is provided.

Keywords: biodiversity, reduced orb-web, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Runcinia* Simon, 1875, is represented by 27 species, of which 12 occur in Africa and eight are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025). Dippenaar-Schoeman (1980) revised the genus, and they were found to be common grass dwellers. Large numbers were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSА) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020).

Runcinia erythrina Jézéquel, 1964 is an African endemic species described from a subadult female from the Ivory Coast in 1964. Blandin (1972) described the male and female. The genus was the first time recorded from South Africa and Zimbabwe in 1980 from 12 localities (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980). In the First Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010) the species was reported from 38 localities. The species is now widespread throughout South Africa and is recorded in all the provinces except the Northern Cape.

METHODS

The voucher specimens sampled during SANSА surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Photographs were also requested for the SANSА Virtual Museum, and photographs of *R. erythrina* were received from several localities (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Runcinia erythrina Jézéquel, 1964

Runcinia erythrina Jézéquel, 1964: 1123(J); Blandin, 1972: 1281–1285(MF); Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980: 312; 1983: 43; 2023: 253; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010: 1044–1045; 2013: 79–81; 2020: 53–54.

Description: Medium-sized (female 4–8 mm (Fig. 1); male 3–4 mm (Fig. 2). Female: Carapace fawn with reddish-brown tint with lateral bands; as wide as long or slightly longer; flattened above;

Figures 1–2. *Runcinia erythrina*. 1. Female dorsal views from Irene. 2. Male dorsal views from Irene. Credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 3–13. *Runcinia erythrina*. 3. Female habitus line drawing, 4–6. Female abdomens. 6. Epigyne. 7. Spermatheca. 8–10. Male habitus. 11. Male palp. 12. Abdominal setae. 13. Eye pattern. Credits: 3, 8. After Blandin (1972). 4–5, 9–10, 13. Peter Webb. 6–7, 11–12. After Dippenaar-Schoeman, (1980).

anterior margin straight, posterior margin concave; surface clothed with numerous irregularly spaced, short spiniform setae. Eyes in two rows; anterior row on the frontal slope, posterior row on the dorsal side; anterior margin is straight medially, with two low tubercles (carinae) on each side; lateral eye larger than median eyes (Fig. 13). Abdomen creamy with a distinct reddish-brown pattern that varies slightly between specimens (Figs 3–5); oval longer than wide; posteriorly rounded; with longitudinal striae following contour of abdomen with rows of dark setae (Fig. 12). Legs fawn; I and II longest; tibiae and metatarsi with strong, paired macrosetae (Fig. 17). Epigyne (Fig. 6). Male: Slenderer than females. Abdominal patterns less distinct or absent (Figs 8–10), with longer legs (Fig. 18). Palp with medium length retrolateral apophysis (Fig. 11).

Figures 14–15. *Runcinia erythrina* female on their egg sacs. Credits: 14–15. Allen Jones.

LIFESTYLE

Runcinia erythrina is a semi-sedentary spider and excels as an ambusher. With their elongated bodies and cryptic colouration, their bodies blend in with the grass. They move freely around on the grass and are mainly active during the day, waiting for prey. They have strong bodies and robust front legs that enable them to attack prey, sometimes larger than themselves (Fig. 17). They construct their egg sacs in grass inflorescences and cover the sac with pieces of grass (Figs 14–15). The males were collected in December, and the females from October to May.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Ivory Coast, Kenya (Kioko *et al.*, 2021), Zimbabwe, Botswana (new record, Thamalakane river NCA) and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: During the SANSa surveys they were mainly sample sweeping the grass and herb layer. The species has been sampled during surveys in the Grassland biome (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Savanna biome (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2013; Foord *et al.*, 2011) and the Fynbos biome (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

In the SANSa database, they have been recorded from 50 localities (for all the localities, see Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020: 53–54). They were sampled during several grassland surveys of which the following results have been published: Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fourie *et al.*, 2023); Golden Gate Highland National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2024); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Zyl, 2023); Tembe Elephant

Figure 16. Map showing the distribution of *Runcinia erythrina* in South Africa.

Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2020); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016); Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023); Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2024).

iNaturalist: Although the species seems to be widely distributed only two entries from Bedford and Paternoster are presently listed.

Figures 17–18. *Runcinia erythrina*. 17. Female on fynbos feeding. 18. Male showing the long legs. Credits: 17–18. Peter Webb.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has a wide distribution it is known from both sexes and is listed as Least Concern. The species is protected in 19 reserves and national parks in South Africa.

REFERENCES

BLANDIN P. 1972. Note sur une espèce rare de thomise de la savane de Lamto (Côte d'Ivoire), *Runcinia (Runciniopsis) erythrina* Jézéquel, 1964 (Araneae-Thomisidae). *Bulletin du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle de Paris* (3) **92**(Zoologie 71): 1281–1285.

DIPPENAAR S.M., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., MODIBA M.A. & KHOZA T.T. 2008. A checklist of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Polokwane Nature Reserve, Limpopo Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 50: 10–17.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 1980. The crab-spiders of southern Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). 1. The genus *Runcinia* Simon, 1875. *Journal of the Entomological Society of South Africa* 43: 303–326.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 1983. The spider genera *Misumena*, *Misumenops*, *Runcinia* and *Thomisus* (Araneae: Thomisidae) of southern Africa. *Entomology Memoir, Department of Agriculture Republic of South Africa* 55: 1–66.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. *Field Guide of the Spiders of South Africa*. Struik Nature 400 pp.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 29–38. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831547>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. FOORD S. H. & HADDAD C. 2013. *Spiders of the Savanna Biome*. University of Venda & Agricultural Research Council, 134 pp

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N., & JOCQUÉ R. 2010. First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae. South African National Survey of Arachnida Technical Report 2010 version 1 1160 pp. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7628809>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R. LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA): a review of current knowledge, constraints, and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70(3): 245–275.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L. N. 2020. The Thomisidae of South Africa. Part 2 My-R. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 67 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7513276

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LYLE R. & VAN DEN BERG A.M. 2012. Bioinformatics on the spiders of South Africa. *Serket* 13 (1/2): 121–127.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & LOTZ L. 2024. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Golden Gate Highlands National Park, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 51: 28–35. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13766555>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & LOTZ L. 2024. The spider diversity of the Karoo National Park, South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae) an updated checklist. *SANSA Newsletter* 52: 37–42. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14524411>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S, VAN DEN BERG A. & PRENDINI L. 2009. A checklist of spiders and scorpions of the Nylsvley Nature Reserve, South Africa. *Koedoe* 50(1): 1–9.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & VAN ZYL J. 2023. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA): Spider diversity of the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve, Gauteng province, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 44: 23–31. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7539738>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., WIESE L. & LOTZ L.N. 2023. Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 47: 33–42. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8420690>

FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.

FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., JOCQUÉ R., HADDAD C.R., LYLE R. & WEBB P. 2016. South African National Survey of Arachnida: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Limpopo province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 58(1), 8 pages a1405. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v58i1.1405>

FOURIE R., HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & GROBLER A. 2013. Ecology of the plant-dwelling spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of the Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve, South Africa. *Koedoe* 55(1), 9 pages. doi: 10.4102/koedoe.v55i1.1113.

HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L.N. & LYLE R. 2013. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Grassland Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 97–122.

HADDAD C.R., HONIBALL A., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & SLOTOW R. 2010. Spiders as potential indicators of elephant-induced habitat changes in the endemic sand forest, Maputaland South Africa. *African Journal of Ecology* 48: 446–460.

JÉZÉQUEL J.-F. 1964. Araignées de la savane de Singrobo (Côte d'Ivoire). III.-Thomisidae. *Bulletin de l'Institut Fondamental d'Afrique Noire* 26(A): 1103–1143.

KIOKO G.M., MARUSIK Y.M., LI S., KIOKO E.N. & JI L. 2021. Checklist of the spiders (Araneae) of Kenya. *African Invertebrates* 62(1): 49–229. <https://doi.org/10.3897/AfrInvertebr.62.58776>

WORLD SPIDER CATALOG 2025. World Spider Catalog. Version 26. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 15/02/25. doi: 10.24436/2